

UPLB READY BATINGAW: INNOVATIVE DISASTER PREPAREDNESS THROUGH SOCIOTECHNICAL APPROACH

Jonathan D. Maliwat, Atty. Eric Paul D. Peralta, Grizelda P. Marza,
Pamela Mai R. Arquiza, Kristine Bernadette T. Matalog, Alva Marie H. Tirones
and Wilfredo M. Mulato, Jr.

Security and Safety Office, University of the Philippines Los Baños

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14288703>

ABSTRACT

The UPLB READY BATINGAW was an innovative initiative that involved a customized early warning system constructed from recyclable materials, hence promoting environmental sustainability. The BATINGAW was implemented in six experimental sites at the University of the Philippines Los Baños. The objective is to improve disaster preparedness by identifying an early warning device as a crucial element to address the absence of emergency alarm systems on campus and during power outages. This study utilized the paper by Khankeh et al., (2019) to systematically review and assess the effectiveness of the early warning system. It employed sociotechnical systems thinking (Davis et al., 2024) to emphasize the significance of social and technical components in understanding and evaluating the efficacy of innovation. The methodologies used in this study are surveys and literature reviews. A total of 85 responses from the academic and non-academic community, including faculty, staff, and students, were collected from the six areas where BATINGAW is situated. Consequently, there were discrepancies and varied reactions from respondents who advocated for promotional efforts of BATINGAW to elevate awareness, which also encompasses the implementation of training and exercises to foster active engagement, ultimately aiming to improve overall campus safety.

Keywords: *BATINGAW, Early Warning System, Disaster Preparedness*

INTRODUCTION

The University of the Philippines Los Baños (UPLB) consistently prioritizes research and development as the primary outcome of its guiding principles of service and excellence. This ethos encourages non-academic personnel to similarly engage in their roles and responsibilities as a support unit within academia. The authors from the Security and Safety Office (SSO) responded to this by developing the UPLB READY BATINGAW. This project originates from the necessity to address the risks of disasters and emergencies on campus, aiming to enhance disaster preparedness by providing critical alerts to the UPLB community regarding potential fires, earthquakes, typhoons, and man-made disasters such as shooting incidents. As a result, there's a need for an early warning system for disasters and emergencies, especially during power interruptions at the university (Alberto & Fababeir, 2024).

The word READY stands for Risk, Emergency, and Disaster-Ready (READY), a program which aims to equip the UPLB community with knowledge and skills necessary to face disasters (Bautista & Romero, 2023). On the other hand, BATINGAW, an acronym for "Babala at Abiso para sa Tiyak Na kaliGtasan ng bAWat isa" (warning and notification for the safety of everyone), addresses the problem of inoperative emergency alarms in essential structures (Marza, 2024).

The recent report on the global multi-hazard early warning system, issued by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) and the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), highlights the significance of early warning systems that incorporates both global and regional initiatives (UNDRR & WMO, 2023).

In accordance with these initiatives, SSO prioritized its responsibility to educate campus personnel, including faculty, staff, and students, on crisis and disaster preparedness, while also formulating campus emergency and disaster policies to ensure compliance with regulatory agencies.

From 2020 to 2023, SSO trained a total of 603 personnel through 17 training activities, including earthquake preparedness, disaster response, and fire safety seminars, conducted in various colleges and offices at the university (Office of the Vice Chancellor for Community Affairs, 2024). Through these activities, the authors identified the absence of emergency alarm systems and the malfunctioning of the fire alarm in the campus building. As a result, an early warning device was developed utilizing recycled resources, such as empty liquid petroleum gas (LPG) tanks, metal chains, and dumbbell weights, thereby creating a sustainable early warning system. Due to this effort, six BATINGAW have been installed at various locations on campus, facilitated by monetary and material contributions from UPLB employees and alumni.

How the new BATINGAW works?

When striking the BATINGAW, it creates a loud sound similar to a church bell. A continuous 15-second strike connotes a fire alert, signaling or alerting the campus. Two continuous 15-second strikes signify typhoon and earthquake emergencies. Lastly, three continuous 15-second strikes indicate a major incident, such as a shooting incident or an active shooter on campus. This system is an official internal policy of the campus, issued

as an office memorandum through the Office of the Chancellor, making it a standard reference for using the BATINGAW.

It was conceptualized early first quarter of this year, the first BATINGAW was launched in March 2024 at the UPLB Student Union (SU) building, the second was in May 2024 at the UPLB SSO (Tirones, 2024), the third BATINGAW was launched in June 2024 at the UPLB College of Human Ecology (CHE), the fourth was installed at the corner of Narra Road and Jose R. Velasco Avenue at the Sacay Guard post in August 2024 (Marza, 2024), the fifth and sixth was located at the UPLB Makiling Residence Hall (MAREHA) dormitory and UPLB Department of Social Sciences - College of Arts and Sciences (DSS-CAS) in September 2024 (Matalog, 2024).

BATINGAW at the UPLB SU building

BATINGAW at the UPLB SSO

BATINGAW at UPLB Sacay Guard

BATINGAW at the UPLB CHE

Research Questions

The research questions focus on three main areas:

1. How aware are the respondents about the BATINGAW?
2. What are the respondent's perception about the BATINGAW?
3. How effective is the BATINGAW and what level of engagement do the respondents exhibit during the study?

The findings of this paper will help to evaluate the initial feedback and provide guidance for the next improvements of BATINGAW to ensure the continued success and sustainability on campus.

Applying Sociotechnical System (STS) theory to UPLB READY BATINGAW

Incorporating STS theory, Abbas & Michael (2023) offers a summary of the idea, which emerged in the 1950s at the Tavistock Institute in London, focusing on the integration of social and technical elements to attain system success. Additionally, there were studies detailing various models and components utilized during emergencies and disasters (Khankeh et al., 2019), including STS principles for system design (Imanghaliyeva et al., 2020), and safety causation in STS (Zarei et al., 2024). This review examines essential literature on the subject, emphasizing the necessity of integrating social and technical components to develop successful early warning systems.

Khankeh et al., (2019) assert that no systematic assessment of the models, structures, and components of early warning systems has been undertaken to date. Identifying various early warning models, their characteristics and components, and analyzing their advantages and disadvantages is crucial for creating a comprehensive model that incorporates vital factors. Like in BATINGAW project it is better to identify the level of effectivity inside the campus.

On the other hand, Zarei et al., (2024) discuss the dynamic interplay between social and technical elements. Applying main elements of this project, it will guide the study to identify the following social and technical elements that will highlights the interaction between the user and technology as well as the use of technology and process on using it. This will direct the study inside the conceptual framework utilizing STS and pinpointing the essential components. It will also assist in composing the survey questionnaire and formulating the research problem for this study.

Imanghaliyeva et al., (2020), explore the historical evolution and theoretical foundations of STS theory, which can be applied to enhance the safety and reliability of early warning systems. By analyzing seventy years of mainstream sociotechnical principles for system design. In applying the historical antecedent for this study of BATINGAW that will be a good foundation to determine if there were same innovation in the past similar to this innovation.

Trogrlić et al., (2022) discussed the roles of the main actors and including the main component of early warning systems. Here, it was mentioned the social components of warning systems as well the different problem like funding and stakeholder engagement.

This study considers the interplay between social and technical aspects within an organizational framework. It emphasizes that both social elements (people, culture and interactions) and technical elements (tools, processes) must be designed and integrated harmoniously to achieve optimal performance and sustainability.

To simplify, and based on the study by Zarei et al. (2024), below are the identified key components of STS, which include both social and technical elements:

Social Elements:

- People: Includes the users, operators, and stakeholders involved.
- Culture and Interactions: The norms, values, and relationships that influence behavior and decision-making.

Technical Elements:

- Technology: The tools, devices, and systems used.
- Processes: The workflows and procedures in place.

Here, in applying these two elements into BATINGAW initiative, the social element was identified as composition of people and cultural interaction, the crucial role of the academic and non-academic personnel such as faculty, staff, and students are critical part that serve as user and decision maker as well as the overall actors. The culture and interactions within the campus is also vital for capacity building in times of disaster to rebound from difficulties. The technical elements combined of technology and processes, incorporating innovative technology made up of recycled materials and the protocols of broadcasting alarms and warning by striking the BATINGAW will definitely prevent any disasters and become controlled through coordinated response coming from critical alerts of BATINGAW. Below is the application context of the conceptual framework and the diagram:

Social Elements:

- People: Students, faculty, staff, and security personnel involved in the emergency response.
- Culture and Interactions: The norms and behaviors around disaster preparedness, the trust in the system, and the cooperation during drills and actual emergencies.

Technical Elements:

- Technology: The UPLB READY BATINGAW device, which use recycled materials such as empty LPG tanks, metal chains, and dumbbell weights.
- Processes: The process for deploying and maintaining the devices, as well as the different sound indicator protocols during emergencies.

Conceptual Framework Diagram:

METHODOLOGY

The evaluation of the UPLB READY BATINGAW program will employ a mixed-methods approach, combining primary and secondary data to provide a comprehensive

assessment of the campaign's impact. The research employs a descriptive approach to evaluate the perceptions, efficacy, and involvement levels of the UPLB community concerning the BATINGAW. The research questions concentrate on respondents' awareness and comprehension of BATINGAW's capabilities. Furthermore, inquiries will concentrate on the effectiveness and reliability, encompassing aspects of adoption and engagement with the BATINGAW system. Finally, about the feedback and recommendations from the responders. The study question aligns with the conceptual framework of STS, encompassing its two principal elements, namely: social and technical.

A total of 85 respondents participated in the survey, which was disseminated across the six selected locations where BATINGAW was situated, facilitating the accurate collection of information regarding the participants' experiences and opinions. The principal data collection instrument is a structured survey questionnaire intended to obtain quantitative data from respondents at UPLB.

Aside from demographics, the questionnaire comprises parts on awareness and perception, efficacy and dependability, adoption and engagement, and feedback and ideas. A random sample method will be utilized to guarantee participation from all principal groupings within the UPLB community, encompassing students, teachers, and staff. The sample size will be established according to the overall population of these groups at UPLB, with the objective of achieving a meaningful number of responses. The aforementioned questionnaire will be disseminated electronically by email and delivered personally to their offices. Participants will be guaranteed the privacy and confidentiality of their responses.

Participants will be informed about the purpose of the study, their rights and identities were also protected, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Data will only use purely for the evaluation of this BATINGAW study and future improvement.

RESULTS

The demographic survey started with the identification of different roles and position in the university considering both academic and non-academic personnel. It is included the service years of the respondents.

The first BATINGAW was installed at the UPLB SU building, there were a total of 29 respondents: 1 student, 9 administrative staff, 7 researchers or REPS (REPS stands for Research, Extension and Professional Services), 10 individual contracts of service or ICS, and 2 job order (JO). With regards to length of service, 10 respondents had been with the institution for less than 1 year, 1-3 years, and more than 5 years, respectively, and 12 respondents associated for 3-5 years.

At the UPLB SSO Headquarters, majority of the 6 respondents are members of the university police or special police, including security officers and guards, all of whom hold permanent plantilla positions. These respondents have diverse lengths of service with

UPLB: 2 have been associated with the institution for less than 1 year, 1 for 1-3 years, and 3 for more than 5 years.

The UPLB CHE survey group consists 5 students, 3 administrative staff, 1 REPS and 1 ICS, with a total of 10 respondents. All 5 respondents have been affiliated with UPLB for more than 5 years. This suggests that the feedback from this group comes from a more seasoned segment of the student body, likely providing well-informed perspectives on the initiative.

In the UPLB Sacay Guard post survey (corner Narra Road and Jose R. Velasco Avenue) there were 10 respondents, all students. The majority (8 respondents) have been at UPLB for 1-3 years, while 2 respondents has been with the institution for less than a year. Since there are relatively new students, who may have a different level of familiarity and engagement with the BATINGAW initiative.

In the UPLB MAREHA dormitory survey, the majority of respondents are administrative staff (9 respondents), with only one student participating. A total of 10 respondents. Most of these respondents have been with UPLB for over 5 years (8 respondents), indicating that the feedback primarily reflects the views of experienced administrative staff members. One respondent has been with UPLB for 1-3 years, and another 1 stayed for 3-5years.

Lastly, the UPLB DSS-CAS survey group has 1 student, 6 faculty members, 8 administrative staff, 2 REPS and 3 JO. A total of 20 respondents. The majority of these 11 respondents have been with UPLB for more than 5 years, 2 respondents are less than 1 year in service, with 6 respondents are 1-3 years of service, and 1 is 3-5 years staying in campus. This suggests that the feedback from this group comes from a combination of long-serving administrative and academic personnel.

Overall, the demographics summary illustrates the varied roles and service durations of the respondents, providing a comprehensive understanding of the perspectives and engagement levels across different groups within UPLB. This diversity of feedback is essential for evaluating the effectiveness and areas for improvement of the BATINGAW initiative.

Table 1. Number of respondents by role

Role	Total Respondent
Faculty	6
Student	18
Administrative Staff	35
REPS	10
ICS	14
JO	2
	85

Here is a summary of the total number of respondents, categorized by their role at UPLB and their years of service:

Table 2. Respondents total years of service

Survey Location	Role	Less than 1 year	1-3 years	3-5 years	More than 5 years	Not Specified	Total
UPLB SU building	Faculty Student Administrative Staff REPS ICS JO	7	9	3	10	-	29
UPLB SSO	Administrative Staff	2	1	-	3	-	6
UPLB CHE	Students Administrative Staff REPS ICS	2	3	-	5	-	10
UPLB Sacay Guard post (Corner Narra Road and Jose R. Velasco Avenue)	Student	2	8	-	-	-	10
UPLB MAREHA dormitory	Student Administrative Staff	-	1	1	8	-	10
UPLB DSS -CAS	Administrative Staff Faculty	2	6	1	11	-	20

DISCUSSION

The following are the key findings and suggestions:

Understanding of BATINGAW device's purpose: Overall, the majority of respondents have a moderate to strong understanding, while others have limited knowledge. This highlights the need for an awareness drive about the BATINGAW's function and purpose.

Table 3. Respondents understanding of BATINGAW's purpose

Not at All	Slightly	Moderately	Significantly	Extremely
4	6	29	31	15
4.71%	7.06%	34.12%	36.47%	17.65%

Participation in drills or training sessions: The majority of respondents did not participate in the drills and training sessions. There is low participation because the project is still new, having been launched approximately nine months ago in March 2024. This highlights the need for strategies to increase participation in practical exercises and the necessity for additional training drills in BATINGAW's function.

Table 4. Respondents involvement in drills and training sessions

Yes	No
28	57
32.94%	67.06%

Effectiveness of drills/training sessions: Although some of the respondents have already participated in previous earthquake and fire drills, those who attended were positively satisfied with the effectiveness of these exercises. However, there is a need for improvement, which calls for regular training and actual demonstrations.

Table 5. Respondents evaluation of drills and training sessions

Not Effective	Slightly Effective	Moderately Effective	Very Effective	Extremely Effective
0	6	16	25	7
0%	11.11%	29.63%	46.30%	12.96%

Confidence in BATINGAW's functionality during outages: Regarding the confidence ratings of respondents, the results were mixed. While some respondents expressed confidence during power outages, others were unsure. It would be beneficial to continue demonstrating BATINGAW's purpose, especially during disaster emergencies and when existing emergency alarm systems are not functioning during power interruptions.

Table 6. Respondents confidence in BATINGAW during power outages

Yes	No	Unsure
55	3	27
64.71%	3.53%	31.76%

Likelihood to follow alerts in an emergency: There were respondents who showed willingness to follow emergency instructions for a safe evacuation. Using the BATINGAW, it creates a loud sound to inform people of potential hazards inside the campus. There is a need to create a trust system with the BATINGAW's functionality.

Table 7. Respondents willingness to follow emergency alerts

Not Likely	Slightly Likely	Moderately Likely	Very Likely	Extremely Likely
0	6	24	29	26
0%	7.06%	28.24%	34.12%	30.59%

Factors encouraging engagement: Key factors that encourage engagement include clear communication of benefits, demonstrated effectiveness, positive peer feedback, and regular training and drills. These insights suggest that transparent communication and practical demonstrations are key to fostering involvement.

Table 8. Respondents additional suggestions for engagement

Clear Communication of its Benefits	Regular Training and Drills	Positive Feedback from Peers	Demonstrated Effectiveness in Real Scenario	Others
47	49	34	63	2
24.10%	25.13%	17.44%	32.31%	1.03%

Suggested improvements: Suggestions include promoting BATINGAW on social media, raising awareness of its purpose, ensuring effective usage, increasing the number of devices in critical areas, and encouraging donations and promotion to barangays and other establishments. Additional suggestions include more training, regular drills, making the BATINGAW instrument louder, and conducting weekly drills to familiarize signals.

Additional comments: Respondents appreciated the initiative and emphasized the importance of ensuring the effectiveness of materials used.

This table summarizes the key findings from the surveys conducted across different offices and groups at UPLB, along with the corresponding observations and suggestions for improvement:

Table 9. Summary of findings and improvement suggestions

Key Findings	Observations	Suggestions
Understanding of BATINGAW Device's Purpose	Different levels of understanding were observed among respondents in various roles, ranging from limited to moderate to strong comprehension.	Greater clarity and increased efforts for awareness and information drives about the BATINGAW's function.

Participation in Drills or Training Sessions	Since the project has only been operational for 9 months, the participation results were low as some groups did not participate at all.	Implement strategies to increase participation in practical exercises, such as better promotion of drills.
Effectiveness of Drills/Training Sessions	The general perception from participants was positive, though there is still room for improvement.	Continuous conduct of regular training and practical demonstrations for easy adaptation of the project, making it more user-friendly.
Confidence in BATINGAW's Functionality During Outages	There are mixed confidence levels among the respondents, with some still unsure as of now.	Increase efforts to test and gather feedback during actual disaster responses to enhance reliability and build trust among the campus personnel.
Likelihood to Follow Alerts in an Emergency	Respondents' responses regarding willingness varied; some have strong trust, while others are hesitant.	Continue to build trust and confidence in the system's guidance through effective use and workshop demonstrations.
Factors Encouraging Engagement	Some identified factors include the benefits of clearer communication, demonstrated effectiveness, positive peer feedback, and regular training and drills.	Ensure transparent communication and conduct practical demonstrations to foster involvement.
Suggested Improvements	Promote on social media to raise awareness of the purpose, ensure effective usage, increase devices in critical areas, and encourage donations and promotion to barangays and establishments.	Implement additional training, regular drills, and weekly drills to familiarize everyone with the signals.
Additional Comments	Respondents appreciate the initiative and emphasize the importance of effective materials.	Ensure the materials used are effective and reliable.

Conclusions

The data indicates that while there is moderate understanding and confidence in the BATINGAW system, there is room for improvement, that's one of the purposes of this research and to establish needed study or future research on how to increase awareness and convince more to participate in drills to enhance engagement. Recommendations include promoting the initiative on promotional activities, and encouraging more active participation and training.

The study emphasizes varying degrees of comprehension, limited engagement in drills, and assurance in the system's dependability. Enhancement should prioritize explicit communication, consistent training, and shown efficacy. Participants advocate for the promotion of BATINGAW, the augmentation of awareness, the assurance of appropriate usage, the proliferation of devices in essential locations, and the solicitation of funds.

Recommendations

Additional recommendations include enhanced training and routine drills to adapt to signals. Addressing these issues can significantly enhance campus safety at UPLB.

- The need to enhance promotional activities for strategic communication of BATINGAW initiative and its purpose, including videos and step-by-step guides, to know how to use the BATINGAW device effectively that will convince all members of the UPLB community.
- Encourage greater participation for both academic and non-academic personnel in BATINGAW drills with practical engagement will help for better understand the system during disaster emergencies. The conduct regular training sessions and drills in various campus buildings and units to ensure widespread familiarity with the system.
- Install more BATINGAW devices in all dormitories and key buildings across the campus to enhance safety and preparedness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors obtained the consent of the respondents while conducting this survey, explaining the purpose of this study and ensuring the protection of the respondent's identities. Additionally, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study, and the authors have approached the research analysis with honesty and impartiality.

Acknowledgements

The acknowledgment goes to the participants, composed of faculty, staff, and students from the six areas where the 'BATINGAW' is located: UPLB SU building, UPLB SSO, UPLB CHE, students staying at the Arable Premier Residences near Sacay Guard post, UPLB MAREHA dormitory, and UPLB DSS-CAS. Their shared time and contribution to the survey have substantially contributed to the analysis of this study.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, R. & Michael, K. (2023) Socio-Technical Theory: A review. In S. Papagiannidis (Ed), TheoryHub Book. Available at <https://open.ncl.ac.uk> / ISBN: 9781739604400
- Alberto, M.A.J. & Fababeir A.J. (2024). UPLB SSO rings towards safety and security with new fire alarm system. Los Baños Times. Retrieved from <https://lbtimes.ph/2024/03/22/uplb-sso-rings-towards-safety-and-security-with-new-fire-alarm-system/>
- Bautista, M.T.C. & Romero, C.J.B. (2023). UPLB launches “READY” program for a disaster-ready campus. University of the Philippines Los Baños. Retrieved from <https://uplb.edu.ph/all-news/uplb-launches-ready-program-for-a-disaster-ready-campus/>
- Davis, M. C., Challenger, R., Jayewardene, D. N. W., & Clegg, C. W. (2014). Advancing socio-technical systems thinking: A call for bravery. *Applied Ergonomics*, 45(2, Part A), 171-180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2013.02.009>
- Imanghaliyeva, A.A., Thompson, P., Salmon, P., Stanton, N.A. (2020). A Synthesis of Sociotechnical Principles for System Design. In: Rebelo, F., Soares, M. (eds) *Advances in Ergonomics in Design. AHFE 2019. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol 955. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20227-9_63
- Khankeh, H.R., Hosseini, S.H., Farrokhi, M. Hosseini, M.A., & Amanat, N. (2019) Early warning system models and components in emergency and disaster: a systematic literature review protocol. *Syst Rev* 8, 315 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-019-1211-5>
- Marza, G.P. (2024). SSO unveils “UPLB READY BATINGAW,” a future-proof fire alarm device. University of the Philippines Los Baños. Retrieved from <https://uplb.edu.ph/all-news/sso-unveils-uplb-ready-batingaw-a-future-proof-fire-alarm-device/>
- Marza, G.P. (2024). SSO unveils 4th “BATINGAW” early warning device. University of the Philippines Los Baños. Retrieved from <https://uplb.edu.ph/all-news/sso-unveils-4-th-batingaw-early-warning-device/>
- Matalog, K.B.T. (2024). SSO, UPSILON donate “BATINGAW” for MAREHA and DSS-CAS. University of the Philippines Los Baños. Retrieved from <https://uplb.edu.ph/all-news/sso-upsilon-donate-batingaw-for-mareha-and-dss-cas/>
- Office of the Vice Chancellor for Community Affairs (2024). End of Term Accomplishment Report 2020-2023
- Tirones, A.M.H. (2024). SSO conducts 2nd rank inspection and 2nd BATINGAW launching. University of the Philippines Los Baños. Retrieved from <https://uplb.edu.ph/all-news/sso-conducts-2nd-rank-inspection-and-2nd-batingaw-launching/>
- Trogrlić, R., van den Homberg, M., Budimir, M., McQuistan, C., Sneddon, A., & Golding, B. (2022). Early warning systems and their role in disaster risk reduction. In *Early Warning Systems and Their Role in Disaster Risk Reduction* (pp. 11-46). Springer.

United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) & World Meteorological Organization (WMO). (2023). Global status of multi-hazard early warning systems 2023. UNDRR & WMO.

Zarei, E., Biglari, B., & Yazdi, M. (2024). Safety causation analysis in sociotechnical systems. In E. Zarei (Ed.), Safety causation analysis in sociotechnical systems: advanced models and techniques (pp. 1-20). (Studies in Systems, Decision and Control; Vol. 541). Springer, Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-62470-4_1